

Approach for monitoring the topography of laser-induced periodic surface structures using a diffraction-based measurement method

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ABSTRACT

Recently, monitoring systems have become crucial components in industrial-scale laser machines to increase process reliability and efficiency. Particularly, monitoring methods have the potential to optimize and ensure the quality of laser surface patterning by indirectly characterizing the surface topography. Here, a diffraction measurement system, based on scatterometry, is used to determine the mean depth of laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) on stainless steel by analyzing the characteristics of the resulting diffraction patterns. To this end, LIPSS were produced with a ps-pulsed laser system operating at a wavelength of 1064 nm. The results reveal that the mean depth of LIPSS can be extracted from the intensity of the captured diffraction orders down to approximately 14 nm. This compact monitoring tool can be easily adapted to industrial-scale laser systems to improve the quality control and stability of surface microtexturing processes.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, nature-inspired functionalized surfaces can be produced on many materials with feature sizes in the micro- and nanoscale range [1]. Among the available manufacturing processes, laser-based techniques are attracting great interest, as they enable high-throughput structuring with a high degree of flexibility and resolutions down to the sub-micron scale [2]. Particularly, laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) are self-assembled micro and sub-micro structures that arise on a material upon irradiation with short and ultra-short laser pulses [3]. Furthermore, the scalability of this method has already been exploited for functionalizing large areas at high throughput [4]. However, monitoring of this process and quality control of the produced structures are essential for ensuring process stability and reproducibility.

The topography of LIPSS is typically measured by ex-situ optical, electron or atomic force microscopy, and relevant parameters, such as periodicity or orientation, can be extracted from Fourier analysis [5]. Therefore, integrating characterization methods as real-time monitoring systems into the process poses a technological challenge. Even though methods like confocal microscopy offer the possibility to characterize topographies at high resolution, their applicability for larger areas is

limited. A promising approach to monitor and evaluate surface topography suitable for large areas is the application of optical systems based on scatterometry. In this context, Michalek et al. have already demonstrated the general ability of this technology to analyze LIPSS-structured areas [6].

In this study, a compact diffraction measurement system designed to measure the patterns reflected from micro-structured surfaces is used to investigate the topography of LIPSS and extract their mean structure depth and spatial periods.

2. Materials and methods

The laser-structuring experiments were conducted on electro-polished stainless steel sheets (AISI 304, X5CrNi18-10) with a thickness of 0.7 mm. The substrates were irradiated using linearly polarized laser radiation (pulse duration of 10 ps, Edgewave PX200, Germany), working at a wavelength of 1064 nm. For all experiments, the focused spot size was 77 μm . The average fluence F and repetition rate were set to constant values of 3.8 J/cm² and 10 kHz, respectively. The hatch distance h was varied from 60 μm to 120 μm in steps of 20 μm , and the pulse-to-pulse distance d_p from 10 μm to 50 μm in steps of 10 μm . Areas of 5 \times 5 mm² were structured for each process condition.

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Fig. 1. Side view of the 3D model of the diffraction measurement system. 1 – laser pointer; 2 – CCD camera; 3 – patterned sample; 4 – mirror; 5 – beam splitter; 6 – polarizers, 7 – lenses. The beam path of laser radiation is depicted as a green line. An exemplary diffraction pattern from a LIPSS-structured field captured with the CCD camera is shown in the red rectangle.

Fig. 2. SEM images of the produced LIPSS with $F = 3.8 \text{ J/cm}^2$, $d_p = 10 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and a) $h = 60 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, b) $80 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, and c) $100 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. The corresponding diffraction images (captured with two different illumination intensities depending on the diffraction order under analysis) for each structured area are also shown. The images of the diffraction patterns were enhanced for better visualization.

The patterned surfaces were evaluated ex-situ after the laser process by an in-house developed optical measurement system (TU Dresden, Germany) based on scatterometry. A detailed description of this system is shown elsewhere [7]. Fig. 1 shows the utilized measurement setup, including the optics, a low-power laser source (0.9 mW) operating at a wavelength of 532 nm, and a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera. The camera captures the obtained diffraction patterns when a structured surface with repetitive patterns is illuminated.

To reduce environmental influences, which might deteriorate the sensitivity of the method, a background correction was applied by subtracting a reference image from the captured diffraction images. This reference picture was taken without a specimen under the measurement device. To avoid intensity saturation of the different diffraction orders, implying a loss of information, the illumination of the laser beam was adjusted using polarizers to maximize the image contrast for each diffraction order under analysis. The area of each diffraction order was calculated by summing the number of pixels corresponding to the particular diffraction order and having an intensity higher than a threshold of 15 grayscale values. This threshold value was taken from the pixels corresponding to the background noise. For statistical validation, five different spots in each LIPSS-structured field were measured and the results were averaged to determine a mean area of each diffraction order. To calculate the spatial period of the LIPSS, the

distance between the 0th and +1st diffraction orders was measured. For this purpose, the system was calibrated with a well-known structured sample with a spatial period of $4.92 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. The topography of the samples was analyzed by confocal microscopy (CM, Sensofar S Neox 3D Surface Profiler, Spain) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, ZEISS Supra 40VP, Germany).

3. Results and discussion

LIPSS were produced on stainless steel substrates by varying the pulse-to-pulse overlap and hatch distance. Surface topographies were characterized by CM, revealing mean structure depths in the range of 14 nm to 142 nm. Fig. 2 shows exemplary SEM images of the produced LIPSS treated with different hatch distances ($h = 60 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, $80 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and $100 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$), and their corresponding diffraction patterns. The resulting mean structure depth measured by CM (see Fig. S1 in supplementary information) is indicated above the SEM images. From the SEM images, two types of LIPSS were identified: low (LSFL) and high-spatial frequency LIPSS (HSFL). They can be distinguished by the spatial period and orientation relative to the radiation polarization indicated by the double arrow in the images [5]. The period for the HSFL lies between 300 nm and 500 nm, and for the LSFL in the range of 800 nm to 1000 nm, whereas the orientation relative to the polarization is perpendicular and

Fig. 3. Mean area of the a) 0th and b) +1st diffraction orders as a function of the mean structure depth of the produced LSFL. The red curves represent the fit functions.

parallel for the LFLS and HSFL, respectively. Only the LSFL are evaluated here because the camera sensor of the used measurement device is too small to capture the ± 1 st diffraction order formed by HSFL.

Fig. 3 shows the dependency of the measured intensity of the 0th (Fig. 3a) and +1st (Fig. 3b) diffraction orders with the mean structure depth of fabricated LSFL. Two different trends can be seen for both orders. In case of the 0th order, the calculated area decays exponentially with increasing structure depth. In addition, from structure depths larger than 100 nm, the intensity of the 0th order is negligible. For the +1st order, the dependency is different. At low depths, the intensity rises with the structure depth, reaching its maximum at around 43 nm. Then, the intensity drops almost linearly and vanishes at a structure depth of around 140 nm. This behavior is already well-known for sinusoidal phase gratings [8]. Furthermore, the processed type of material may affect the resulting diffraction images [9], although similar trends for both diffraction orders as a function of structure depth can be expected.

The observed behaviors were then fitted by an exponential decay function for the 0th order, and by a 5th-order polynomial function for the +1st diffraction order. The fitting curves are shown in red in Fig. 3 and have a coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.994 and 0.979, respectively (see Table S1 and S2 in the supplementary information section).

Due to the characteristic of the curves in Fig. 3, a combined analysis of the intensities of both 0th and +1st orders can allow the precise determination of the mean structure depth of LSFL using the presented approach. Whereas the measured intensity of the 0th order enables an accurate description of the LIPSS depth up to 70 nm, above this value, the information from the +1st order can be used (up to 130 nm). In this context, an algorithm was written to retrieve both the period and depth of the fabricated LSFL. For example, the textured surface shown in Fig. 2a retrieved areas of 7 and 25,633 pixels for the 0th and +1st orders, respectively. Then, the algorithm estimated a structure depth of 84 nm, roughly 16 % different from the measured topography using CM (96.6 nm). The distribution of periods of the produced LIPSS was estimated from the width of the +1st orders [5], obtaining a period range between 800 and 1200 nm with an average value of 1029 nm. This value is similar to the average period calculated from the SEM images (905 nm, 12 % difference). Table S3 in the supplementary section provides the retrieved mean structure depth and period values for all fields. Due to its compact design, this monitoring system can be implemented for in-line structure quality control during LIPSS manufacturing. It is worth noting that the method can be applied to any material patterned with LIPSS as long as its reflectivity guarantees a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio in the obtained images. Furthermore, the LIPSS spatial period must be larger

than the illumination wavelength so that the first diffraction orders can emerge.

4. Conclusions

LIPSS were produced on stainless steel by applying ps-laser radiation. It was shown that by analyzing the patterns collected by the diffraction measurement system, clear relationships between the measured area for the 0th and +1st orders and the structure depth of LSFL were found. In this way, the developed procedure calculated the depth and period of the LIPSS with high accuracy. In addition, this method for monitoring LIPSS with different geometrical parameters can be easily integrated as an in-line tool to keep track of the produced microtexture. This approach will be evaluated in the future.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Nikolai Schröder: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Data curation. **Christoph Fischer:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Marcos Soldera:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Felix Bouchard:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Bogdan Voisiat:** Software, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andrés Fabián Lasagni:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2022.132794>.

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